

Evaluation Impact of the Brand on the Marketing Performance of Firms

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Abstract

Nowadays, with the increased competition in all business areas having a brand is not a choice, rather it is an inevitable necessity that eventually will cause increase profitability and create competitive advantage. The brand is something that is caused the difference between vessels containing sugar, flour, mineral water and soft drinks. Marketing is an organizational task and a set of transaction processing that has need to a large amount of work and skill

In the marketing world today, brand personality has attractive and charisma concept. The brand's share can be developed through good management of customer relationship, honoring to the customer, and also according to customer's needs, successfully. Given these issues in this study, we want to examine impact of the brand on the marketing performance of firms with providing definitions and concepts of the brand in the area of firms' marketing activity and show its significance in this field

Keyword: Brand, Brand Equity, Marketing, Marketing Management, Marketing Strategy

Introduction

One of the most famous and perhaps most important marketing concepts today that formed for the first time in the 1980s is the concept of brand. The concept first has been proposed as the most important research areas in consumer markets.

Nowadays, with the increased competition in all business areas having a brand is not a choice, rather it is an inevitable necessity that eventually will cause increase profitability and create competitive advantage.

Marketing is an organizational task and a set of transaction processing that has a need for a large amount of work and skill. Accordingly marketing management means exchange groups in order to reach an agreement over the common instances.

Previous Research

No.	Researchers	Results About Brand
1	Chernatony & Segal-Horn (2001)	Dimensions subject was emphasized (Fixation Stability and Values)
2	Grace & O'Cass (2005)	Dimensions of brand was investigated in the form of brand evidence and brand communications (Controlled and Uncontrolled)
3	Berry & Seltman (2007)	Customer experience, organizational values
4	Berry (2000)	Value brand share, external communications, customer experience from organization, concept of brand, awareness of brand, displayed brand
5	Brady& Bourdeau (2005)	Symptoms of internal (national recognition, media coverage, and ranking), Symptoms of external (price, advertising and referrals Pioneers

Defined by Brand

The brand is part of the operational and emotional (Feeling) characteristics that customer to a goods or services. Brand helps to compete with firms. Also, it is a helpful tool to the customer when deciding on purchasing.

In fact, Brand is something that is caused the difference between vessels containing sugar, flour, mineral water and soft drinks. The brand is marker tangible and intangible characteristics that consumer is attached to a product or a type of service. These features were seen in the name, mark, symbols or a combination of these items.

History of Brand

Center for the brand valued was established first time in 1996 by David Hays in the London. This center opened their first international office in the United States of America and then established the offices in 2000 in the Singapore and Australia. Currently, a worldwide network of offices and partners is active in 20 countries around the World.

Benefits of the Brand Identified

1. Directs consumers to choose
2. Increase on the customer loyalty
3. Makes it possible to enter new markets
4. Makes it possible to increase product prices
5. Increases employment staff

Importance of the Brand

Nowadays, with the increased competition in all business areas having a brand is not a choice, rather it is an inevitable necessity that eventually will cause increase profitability and create competitive advantage.

Nowadays, if the brand for organizations is not valuable par with financial assets and their technological, unmistakable, it isn't less valuable to them. This topic is important so that experts in this field know the brand as the character and brand characters can state core and the nearest variable in the consumer decision making when purchasing. Many companies especially those that have a brand of systems have found that creating a successful brand is needy mobilize the whole organization. Every aspect of the organization, including the behavior and performance of employees especially those that are active in the field communication with customers and also heads of the companies, should be aware the value of the brand and always reflect in their work.

Trust to Brand

Chadhari and Holbrooke (2001) define a trusted brand as tendency an average consumer to rely on the ability of the brand to stated commitments. In particular, trust is caused decreases uncertainty in the environment consumers in it are vulnerable because they know can have relied on a trusted brand.

Brand Equity

In the evaluation brand equity from the consumer's perspective unlike financial perspective brand hasn't valued, rather should be valued by consumers. In this way the evaluation of brand depends on information consumer has achieved, felt, seen or heard based on their experiences during the time.

Model Brand of Equity

Awareness of Brand

It is the ability to a potential purchaser for recognition or recalls so that brand belongs to a particular class of product. If a brand is the first name that comes remember its name is the best name in terms of awareness.

Perceived Quality of the Brand

Boulding and associates (1993) define these criteria as consumer awareness superior quality of products than other products. In other words, it is the perception of the customer from overall quality or superiority of a product or service than customer willingness to its replaces. Zeithmal and Bitner (1996) expressed perceived quality isn't the actual quality of the product, rather it is a subjective assessment of consumer about the product.

Mental Association of the Brand

In terms of Crosno and associates (2009) this criterion is a reflection of mental associations and deep attitudes of the consumer about the brand. In terms of Acker is defined brand association everything that associated in the memory with the brand. Brand associations are everything related brand in mind, and it can be including consumer mentality, product characteristics, indications, associations related to organizations, brand character, and symbols.

Loyalty to Brand

It is a position show how likely is that a customer turned another brand, especially when a brand creates a change in the prices and other product features. (Seyed Javadian & Shams 2007)

The Final Value of Brand Equity

It is defined as differences in the value of a product with the brand and other products with the same quality and characteristics but without brand. (Kim & Hone 2010)

Types of Brand Equity

In the marketing studies, brand equity is divided into two categories:

First group, including customer perceptions, such as awareness of brand, brand associations or perceived quality

The second group, included customer behavior, such as loyalty to brand and focus on price differences

Marketing

Marketing refers to a process that is guided all activities related to researchers, production, distribution, and sale of goods from pre-production until after sales during it. (Kotler 2012)

Marketing Management

It is planning process, and implementation of the imagination, pricing, advertising, promotion and distribution of ideas, products and services intend to perform the transaction that is lead to provide individual and organizational goals.

Marketing Strategy

Marketing strategy is an integrated set from the selection so that in the long-term how do create value and appreciate it.

Factors of Marketing Strategy

1. Identify utility opportunities
2. Creating of competitive advantage
3. Challenge of competitive advantage
4. Create of partnership advantage

Marketing and Brand

In the marketing world today, brand personality has attractive and charisma concept. The brand's share can be developed through good management of customer relationship, honoring to the customer, and also according to customer's needs, successfully.

One required capabilities or competencies for success in the arena of competitive are entitlement marketing knowledge and skills in the economic enterprises. Maybe perceived clearly, one of the factors influencing on the being faint of state agencies in terms of competitiveness in the international arena is difficulties related to scientific and operations development of marketing in the economic enterprises. Many factors can play a role in the lack of successful marketing programs. One most important factor is subject to brand and branding that is not the large attention to it.

Nowadays the branding and brand management have several fans in the world of marketing. Build a powerful brand in the market is the target of many firms. Successful brands are caused the increased trust to intangible products and services, and customers are able to visualization and better identification. Customer relationship is one of the best ways for increasing and growth and progress brand value. Emphasis on quality of relationship could lead to more brand value and create a favorable brand image. Among the tangible aspects, a product or service brand image is the most important thing that most marketing strategies are focused on it and they have tended to highlight brand. For this purpose, service sectors tried communicating with customers and through impact has on the customer perception from received services create desired image in the customer's mind.

Conclusions

Nowadays, with the increased competition in all business areas having a brand is not a choice, rather it is an inevitable necessity that eventually will cause increase profitability and create competitive advantage.

The brand is part of the operational and emotional (Feeling) characteristics that customer to a goods or services. Brand helps to compete with firms. Also, it is a helpful tool to the customer when deciding on purchasing.

Brand identified has benefits such as directs of consumers to choose, increase the customer loyalty, possible to enter new markets, possible to increase product prices, and also increases employment staff.

In the evaluation brand equity from the consumer's perspective unlike financial perspective brand hasn't valued, rather should be valued by consumers. In this way the evaluation of brand depends on information consumer has achieved, felt, seen or heard based on their experiences during the time.

The branding and brand management have several fans in the world of marketing. Build a powerful brand in the market is the target of many firms. Successful brands are caused the increased trust to intangible products and services, and customers are able to visualization and better identification. Among the tangible aspects, a product or service brand image is the most important thing that most marketing strategies are focused on it and they have tended to highlight brand.

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